

Complex formation of some transition metals with thiazole Schiff bases^ψ

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Manuscript received 6 April 2005. revised 25 August 2005, accepted 9 September 2005

Abstract : Proton-ligand stability constants of five Schiff bases, derived from 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and R substituted salicylaldehyde (R = H, 5-CH₃, 4-CH₃ and 5-Br) or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, and formation constants of their transition metal (Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) complexes have been determined pH-metrically at room temperature (25 °C) and at constant ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), in 75 : 25% (v/v) ethanol-water medium using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti. The order of stability constants of the complexes has been proposed, which is in accordance with the order suggested by Irving-Williams.

The effect of elevated temperature (35 °C and 45 °C) on the determination of formation constants of metal complexes has been studied. Decrease in value of formation constant of the complex with increase in temperature indicates that low temperature is favorable for complex formation. The thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) at different temperatures have been calculated.

Keywords : Transition metals, thiazole, Schiff base.

In our earlier communication¹, we have reported synthesis of metal (Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and R substituted salicylaldehyde (R = H, 5-CH₃, 4-CH₃ and 5-Br) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The complexes possess 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry and an octahedral geometry (ML₂ type complexes) and are found to be thermally stable. The Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes exhibit good antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*.

In the present communication we describe the pH metric study of complex formation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with thiazole Schiff bases SBPAT [*N*-(salicylidene)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole], 5-MSBPAT [*N*-(5-methylsalicylidene)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole], 4-MSBPAT [*N*-(4-methylsalicylidene)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole], 5-BSBPAT [*N*-(5-bromosalicylidene)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole] and HNBPAT [*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole]. The study has been performed in ethanol-water medium 75 : 25% (v/v) at room

Schiff base	R
SBPAT	H
5-MSBPAT	5-CH ₃
4-MSBPAT	4-CH ₃
5-BSBPAT	5-Br
HNBPAT	

temperature using Calvin- Bjerrum pH metric technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti².

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were distilled before use. The Schiff bases were prepared

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^ψThe paper has been presented at 41st Annual Convention of Chemists (2004).

in the laboratory by using the method as reported earlier¹. The purity of Schiff bases was checked by single spot TLC. All the ligands gave satisfactory carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses.

The solutions of metal salts were prepared in double distilled water free from CO₂. The pH metric titrations were performed against standard alkali (NaOH) solution as under.

(i) *Acid titration* : A mixture [2 ml 0.2 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 7 ml distilled water + 30 ml ethanol] was titrated against standard alkali (NaOH).

(ii) *Schiff base titration* : A mixture [2 ml 0.2 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 10 ml ligand solution + 7 ml distilled water + 20 ml ethanol] was titrated against stan-

dard alkali (NaOH).

(iii) *Metal-ligand titration* : A mixture [2 ml 0.2 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 10 ml ligand solution + 2 ml metal solution + 5 ml distilled water + 20 ml ethanol] was titrated against standard alkali (NaOH).

The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at different temperatures using Elico-4T-120 pH meter coupled with combined glass electrode.

Results and discussion

Proton ligand stability constant (p*K*) values of the ligands SBPAT, 5-MSBPAT, 4-MSBPAT, 5-BSBPAT and HNBPAT were calculated using half integral method. The values are summarized as ligand p*K* (°C) : SBPAT 10.92

Table 1. Metal ligand stability constants of Schiff bases with transition metal ions in ethanol-water medium (75 : 25 %) (v/v) at constant ionic strength *I* = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Sr. no.	Ligand	Temp. (°C)	Metal ion	Stability constants	
				log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ₂
1.	5-MSBPAT	25	Zn ²⁺	7.48	6.42
			Co ²⁺	7.47	6.41
			Ni ²⁺	7.45	6.40
			Cu ²⁺	7.40	6.33
2.	4-MSBPAT	25	Zn ²⁺	6.79	5.72
			Co ²⁺	6.77	5.71
			Ni ²⁺	6.79	5.77
			Cu ²⁺	6.74	5.69
		35	Zn ²⁺	6.44	5.64
			Co ²⁺	6.55	5.63
			Ni ²⁺	6.40	5.61
			Cu ²⁺	6.43	5.53
		45	Zn ²⁺	6.10	5.52
			Co ²⁺	6.15	5.50
			Ni ²⁺	6.06	5.44
			Cu ²⁺	6.09	5.40
3.	5-BSBPAT	25	Zn ²⁺	6.76	5.73
			Co ²⁺	6.80	5.80
			Ni ²⁺	6.73	5.74
			Cu ²⁺	6.75	5.72
4.	SBPAT	25	Zn ²⁺	6.70	5.74
			Co ²⁺	6.76	5.73
			Ni ²⁺	6.74	5.70
			Cu ²⁺	6.71	5.70
5.	HNBPAT	25	Zn ²⁺	6.27	5.30
			Co ²⁺	6.30	5.29
			Ni ²⁺	6.28	5.32
			Cu ²⁺	6.27	5.23

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of metal complexes of 4-MSBPAT

Sr no.	Cation	log K_1			$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$-\Delta H$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		
		25°C	35°C	45°C	I	II	III	I	II	I	II	III
1.	Zn ^{II}	6.79	6.44	6.10	38.74	37.97	36.95	68.53	55.37	98.18	99.22	60.12
2.	Co ^{II}	6.77	6.55	6.15	38.56	38.62	36.85	38.76	64.40	45.45	88.65	88.85
3.	Ni ^{II}	6.79	6.40	6.06	38.68	37.74	36.31	66.77	62.72	97.41	98.89	84.47
4.	Cu ^{II}	6.74	6.43	6.09	38.34	37.85	38.47	52.71	33.22	48.22	48.24	66.77

(25 °C); HNBPAT 10.62 (25 °C); 5-MSBPAT 11.50 (25 °C); 4-MSBPAT 11.27 (25 °C), 11.13 (35 °C), 11.06 (45 °C); 5-BSBPAT 11.12 (25 °C).

The ligand contains only one pK value due to dissociable proton of the phenolic-OH group. The protonation of imino nitrogen (HC=N) does not take place in the pH range under study. The pK values of the ligands follow the trend : 5-MSBPAT > 4-MSBPAT > 5-BSBPAT > SBPAT > HNBPAT and it is explain on the grounds of basic nature of azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen³.

In case of HNBPAT, due to delocalisation of electron density over fused rings the basicity of azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen decreases as compared to that of SBPAT in which there are no substituents on the phenyl ring. Hence proton-ligand stability constant value in HNBPAT is lower than that of SBPAT. Higher pK for 5-BSBPAT, as compared to SBPAT, may be due to the presence of Br in the aromatic ring where it behaves more as electron releasing group via stronger mesomeric effect (+M) rather than electron withdrawing group through -I effect (inductive effect). Such effect may increase the donor ability of azomethine nitrogen in 5-BSBPAT relative to SBPAT and hence proton ligand stability constant value increases.

In the ligands 5-MSBPAT and 4-MSBPAT, methyl group is substituted in phenyl ring. Methyl group has +I effect and therefore electron density on phenyl ring increases. Thus azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen become more basic due to increase in electron density over them and therefore stability constant values of these ligands are higher than that of 5-BSBPAT.

Metal-ligand stability constants :

The titration curves of acid, ligands and the metal ions are studied. The metal ion curve shows departure from ligand curves at pH much lower than the pH of hydrolysis of metal ion and therefore the liberation of proton is due to chelation⁴. The metal ligand stability constants were determined by using half integral method and the values are summarized in Table 1.

The order of stability of Schiff base complexes fol-

lows the trend : Zn > Co > Ni > Cu and it is found to be in accordance with the order suggested by Irving and Williams⁵.

To study the effect of temperature on complexation, we have chosen Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of a representative Schiff base (4-MSBPAT) for the determination of metal-ligand stability constants at 35 and 45°C in ethanol-water (75 : 25%) (v/v) medium and at constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄). The values of the metal-ligand stability constants are summarized in Table 1. As the temperature increases, the values of metal-ligand stability constant decrease suggesting that low temperature is favorable for complexation.

The thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) have been calculated and are summarized in Table 2. The log K values decrease with increase in temperature for complexation. The ΔG , ΔH values are negative, while ΔS values are positive.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the authorities of Solapur University, Solapur and Shivaji University, Kolhapur for providing research facilities. One of the authors (B.N.M.) is thankful to U.G.C. for the award of a teacher fellowship.

References

1. P. G. More and R. B. Bhalvankar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 474; 2004, **81**, 13.
2. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
3. P. Gurkan and N. Gunduz, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 713; S. D. Naikwade, P. S. Mane and T. K. Chondhekar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 41; P. Sanyal, P. Sar and G. P. Sengupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 614; R. K. Pardeshi, N. G. Palaskar and T. K. Chondhekar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 958.
4. T. R. Harkins and H. Freiser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1143; H. T. S. Britton, *Endeavour*, 1943, **2**, 150.
5. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.